

Received: 5 May 2026

Accepted: 6 May 2026

Published: 2 June 2026

Disclosure

In preparing this publication, one of the co-authors, Iryna Izarova, used the Gemini 3.1 Pro LLM (paid tier) to assist with English editing. All the co-authors reviewed, edited, and finalized the output and take full responsibility for and ownership of this content.

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to express their gratitude to the experts involved in the preparation of this statement, namely Dr Maya Khater (United Arab Emirates University) and Prof. Qerim Qerimi (University of Pristina and the Venice Commission).

Declaration of interests

The authors hold leadership roles within the European Association of Science Editors: Bahar Mehmani (President), Iva Grabarić Andonovski (Vice President), Are Brean (Vice President), Iryna Izarova (Chair of the EASE Regional Chapter Committee), and Cem Uzun (Past President and ESE Editorial Board Member). Although European Science Editing is the official journal of the Association, the authors were not involved in the editorial review or the decision-making process for this manuscript. The authors declare no other financial or personal relationships that could be perceived as a conflict of interest regarding this work.

Funding

The authors declare that this study received no financial support.

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Editorial

European Association of Science Editors statement on the escalation of armed conflict in the Middle East and its impact on the global editors' community

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Citation

Mehmani B, Grabarić Andonovski I, Brean A, Uzun C, Izarova I. European Association of Science Editors statement on the escalation of armed conflict in the Middle East and its impact on the global editors' community. *Eur Sci Ed.* 2026;52:e198522.

<https://doi.org/10.3897/ese.2026.e198522>

The European Association of Science Editors (EASE) issues this statement in support of its members and regional chapters across the Middle East and beyond, particularly in Azerbaijan, Egypt, Iran, Iraq, Israel, Oman, Saudi Arabia, the United Arab Emirates, and the United States, as well as the broader scholarly community affected by the ongoing escalation of armed conflict

EASE is a non-political organization; however, we emphasize that scientific progress and scholarly collaboration fundamentally require an environment of peace and stability.

As a global community of scholarly editors and communication professionals, EASE remains dedicated to building trust in research by raising editorial excellence.¹ We are proud of our inclusive and diverse network,² which values different cultures and perspectives. Today, we are deeply concerned for the safety of our members and colleagues, and profoundly saddened by the tragic escalation of hostilities and gross human rights violations in the region and beyond.³ We recognize that the pursuit of knowledge and the integrity of scholarly communication are deeply imperilled by armed conflict. We extend our support to all those striving to uphold academic and editorial standards under extraordinarily difficult circumstances.

Our vision is to nurture a network united by a passion for quality and integrity. We believe that research and scholarly publishing

are global endeavours that should operate beyond political constraints. However, integrity also demands that we uphold the core idea that all disputes must be settled by peaceful means, in such a manner that international peace, security, and justice are not endangered.

Guided by our values of being inclusive and approachable,⁴ we remain committed to creating a safe, supportive space where everyone feels they belong. To that end, we commit to the following measures:

- We will continue to support editors and researchers in conflict zones.
- We invite all to take into account the psychological safety of their colleagues, authors, reviewers, and editors from the impacted countries who either live there or have family members there.
- We recommend reaching out to the handling editors – if your journal has any from an affected region – with compassion to agree on the best way to manage their workload and manuscripts, especially when internet access is limited.
- We encourage journals to consider extending deadlines for authors and reviewers in these regions. If a corresponding author is unreachable, editors should consider temporarily transferring that role to a co-author located outside the region to ensure research progress is not stalled.
- Although we champion editorial excellence and support individuals, EASE, as a matter

of its institutional policy, does not support or partner with entities funded or controlled by states engaged in acts of aggression that violate international law and UN resolutions.

Through ongoing improvement and integrity in everything we do, we aim to help build lasting trust in research and scholarly publishing, even – and especially – during times of global crisis and recovery afterwards.^{5,6}

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11 May 2026

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